

OLONITE THEORY OF PUBLIC FINANCE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH / DEVELOPMENT (2019) EXPLAINED

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ABSTRACT

This study analysed the Keynesian theory of public finance and economic growth and the Wagner's Law of ever increasing state activities. The study used the secondary data from CBN 2019. The Real Gross Domestic Product formed the dependent variable and the independent variable of interest were the Capital Spending on Economic Services, and Spending of Transfers. The variables were validated by conducting the unit root test using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Perron Test (PP), and the correlation coefficient were determined using STATA and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation. A multiple regression model was employed for the study and was analysed using the Generalized Least Squares (GLSs) with the aid of Eviews 11 statistical program. The results of the study indicate that Capital Spending on Economic Services has a positive and significant impact on Economic Growth while Spending on Transfer has a negative and insignificant impact on Economic Growth.

The study recommends that Capital Spending on Economic Services should be maintained and increased and Spending on Transfer should be made Zero, also, the government should develop the refineries to start mass production in order to null off the negative effect of transfers (subsidy payment on oil import and price equalization).

Many have been acquainted with old theories, methodologies and frameworks, forgetting the implications of time, sequences and phenomenon.

The Olonite Theory of Public Finance and Economic Growth/Development is recommended to be used in academics and beyond by students, governments, researchers, etc.

Keywords: Public Spending, Economic Growth, Capital Spending on Economic Services, Spending on Transfer, Nigeria, Central Bank of Nigeria, Statistical Bulletin.

INTRODUCTION

Public spending is a key instrument being employed by the government in controlling economic activities. The importance of public spending towards the functioning of any economy if developed, under developed or developing cannot be ignored. Many Public Finance and

Economic Growth/Development theories have been propounded by different scholars and have been adopted for years however, some have been faulted by this study and a new theory has been propounded to fill the gaps in the faulted theories. The faulted theories are: the Keynesian Theory and Economic Growth Model (1936), and the Wagner's Law (1883).

The Keynesian Theory and Economic Growth Model (1936): The public expenditure is seen as a policy instrument which can be used exogenously, because it is considered to impact economic growth and correct long-term and short-term cyclical imbalances. He asserted that Public expenditure is a cause which affect economic growth, thus the link for casualty can be seen from public expenditure to economic growth and not the other way round. In Keynesian hypothesis, demand can be treated as a foundation for growth. His analysis affirmed that economic performance may be improved by managing the demand policies. The Keynesian theory and economic growth models in general, study public expenditures as an element which affects economic growth in an economy. Specifically, He argued that the impact of public spending on growth is likely to take a positive or negative direction.

Keynes theory was faulted on the following bases:

- i. The theory failed to capture the importance of the Public Finance Management Theory by Erik Lindhal in 1919 which should have been a basis for all public finance theories.
- ii. Expenditure on Transfer was not captured as the model only fit into the economic situation of that time hence the theory has been weakened by "time" and "occurrences".
- iii. That the impact of public spending on growth is likely to take a positive or negative direction was not explicitly spelt out because Keynes (1936) has only aggregated the public spending.

Wagner's Law (1883): This theory is known as the increasing state spending; the theory holds that as the income expands over time, the public expenditure rises. The theory affirms that income growth is a cause which impact public expenditure, thus the link for casualty can be seen from income growth to public expenditure. This theory disagreed with the Keynes theory of public finance (1936).

Wagner's Law (1883) was faulted on the following bases:

- i. There must be a cause and effect factor for an economy development. Wagner claims that as the income expands over time, the activities and functions of government increases. For

Wagner to have selected the dependent variable of choice (public spending) the question is “*what determines income’s growth?*”

- ii. Since there is no bases for the drivers of economy development, this study believes any other assertion on Wagner’s claim is baseless, as he had further submitted that causality runs from economy growth to public spending and not the other way round.

Based on the gaps identified, this study developed some hypotheses, a model by adding expenditure on transfer to fill the gap in the Keynesian theory and economic growth model (1936), and disaggregate the capital expenditure, gathered data and ran the regression analysis including the Pairwise Granger Causality Test to see the direction of causality as claimed by Keynes (1936) and Wagner’s Law (1883) which can be seen in table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Summary of Regression Result

VARIABLES (MODEL)	CECOS (IDV)	CSOCS (IDV)	EXTRF (IDV)	R ²	Adj. R ²	F- Stat
GDP (DV) Coeff. (Sig.)	41314.48 (0.0487)	-16811.24 (0.8809)	-33759.03 (0.2776)	0.738309 (74%)	0.666939 (67%)	10.344
Akaike Info criterion: 34.64727	Schwarz Info criterion: 34.83608	Hannan-Quinn criter.: 34.64526	Probability 0.001563	-	-	-

Source: Extraction from Regression result, 2019; Significance Level is at **5%

Note: Sig. means Probability level and Significance, Coeff. means Coefficient, IDV means Independent Variable, DV means Dependent Variable, CECOS means Capital Expenditure on Economic Services, CSOCS means Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services and EXTRF means Expenditure on Transfer.

Table 1 shows the summary of the regression analysis on the variables. The Akaike Info criterion, Schwarz Info criterion and Hannan-Quinn Criter showed the goodness of fit for the model, as their figures stood at 34.64727, 34.83608 and 34.64526 respectively and the P-value is $0.001563 < 0.05$.

Table 2: Pairwise Granger Causality Test

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

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Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
CECOS does not Granger Cause RGDP RGDP does not Granger Cause CECOS	14	7.82283 2.12385	0.0174 2.9946
CSOCS does not Granger Cause RGDP RGDP does not Granger Cause CSOCS	14	0.19062 1.57843	0.6708 0.2350
EXTRF does not Granger Cause RGDP RGDP does not Granger Cause EXTRF	14	0.13012 0.31290	0.7251 0.5871
CSOCS does not Granger Cause CECOS CECOS does not Granger Cause CSOCS	14	0.06244 0.10493	0.8073 0.7521
EXTRF does not Granger Cause CECOS CECOS does not Granger Cause EXTRF	14	15.5109 7.06660	0.0023 0.0223
EXTRF does not Granger Cause CSOCS CSOCS does not Granger Cause EXTRF	14	1.99159 0.12141	0.1858 0.7341

Source: *Eviews 11 Result, 2019:*

Note: *Obs. means Observations, Prob. means Probability Level.*

From table 2, the result of Pairwise Granger Causality Test shows that only Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (CECOS) has significant causal impact on the Gross Domestic Product in the period under review while the other explanatory variables capital expenditure on social and community services (CSOCS) and expenditure on transfer (EXTRF) are not significant in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth.

In the light of the above findings, this study developed a public spending and economic growth/development theory that fill all the gaps listed above. The theory is called “Olonite Theory of Public Finance and Economic Growth/Development”.

Table 3: Olonite Theory of Public Finance and Economic Growth / Development (2019)

Version	Functions and Notations	Valid when
Olonite Theory of Public Finance and Economic	Gross Domestic Product = f(Public Spending)	$\beta > 0$
	Gross Domestic Product = f(Recurrent Expenditure, Capital Expenditure, Transfer)	
	$GDP_t = \alpha + \beta * PS_t^{\theta, \downarrow, \uparrow, 0} + \varepsilon_t$	

Growth/Development (2019)	$GDP_t^{\rightarrow\uparrow} = \alpha + \beta*(REEXP, CAEXP, EXTRF)_t^{\Theta, \downarrow, \uparrow, 0} + \varepsilon_t$	
	$GDP_t^{\rightarrow\uparrow} = \alpha + \beta*(REEXP^{\downarrow}, CAEXP^{\Theta(\downarrow a-or-d-fs)\downarrow}, EXTRF^{0(\downarrow a-or-d-f)})_t + \varepsilon_t$	
	$GDP_t^{\rightarrow\uparrow} = \alpha + \beta*(REEXP^{\downarrow}, CAEXP^{\Theta(\downarrow a-or-d-fs)\downarrow}, EXTRF^{0(\downarrow a-or-d-f)})_t + \varepsilon_t$	

Source: Author's Computation and Design 2019;

Notes: “→↑” means: “to increase”, “↓” means: “reduce”, “↕” means: “increase and reduce”, “0” means: “make zero”. “Θ” means: “some”, PS denotes Public Spending, GDP means Gross Domestic Product, “i” means non-performing, “a-or-d-fs” means aggregated or disaggregated functions.

Explaining table 3, it can be deduced that not all Government Expenditure drive economic growth. Public spending comprises of the recurrent expenditure, capital expenditure and expenditure on transfer. The recurrent expenditure and expenditure on transfer won't drive economic growth since they are consumption expenditures. They won't drive economic growth; the capital expenditure is an investment spending which this study believes drives economic growth. In light of this, this study claim that recurrent expenditure should be kept minimal since it can't be equal to zero, as an increase in the capital expenditure will definitely expand the recurrent expenditure, though not in the same proportion. Some capital expenditure should be increased in particular, the performing functions while some functions decreased and this should be observed in respect to the public finance management theory by Erik Lindhal in 1919 and expenditure on transfer should be made to zero especially, the non performing functions since it has a negative impact on the economic growth. To reduce the recurrent expenditure and increase the capital spending, the Public Private Partnership (PPP) should be encouraged.

The Olonite Theory of Public Finance and Economic Growth/Development is recommended to be used in academics and beyond by students, governments, researchers, etc.

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